

Essays on Modelling Public-Private-Partnerships (PPP) for Emergency Medical Services

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ABSTRACT

Medical emergencies occur anywhere, at any time, in any country irrespective of whether it is a developed, developing or an underdeveloped country. These emergencies occur by the hour, consuming a lot of resources and sometimes, without even achieving the desired results, i.e., to save lives. Medical emergencies have been around since the start of the human civilization, however, they gained recognition as a specialty only around 30 years ago (Chung, 2001). An emergency medical system's goal should be to provide universal and integrative emergency care right from the time it receives information from an emergency user (Dykstra, E. H, 1997). Further, in a country like India, the seventh largest country, and with the second highest population in the world (David, S. S., & Vasnaik, M, 2007) and high income disparity, the implementation and context of the emergency medical system should be in a way to increase health equity and not worsen the current health disparities (David, S. S., & Vasnaik, M, 2007). This challenge faced by India and similar developing nations can be attended to by promoting systematic development of an evidence-based emergency medical system that is more cost-effective than those in developed countries like the USA, Canada and certain European countries where there is lesser income disparity. To design an effective emergency medical system, there is need to address questions such as how it would integrate with the current health-care infrastructure, local communities as well as their values, and the financial resources that would be needed to augment the services step by step (Gupta, M. Das, & Rani, M. 2004). In India, the public sector accounts for less than 20 percent of the total healthcare expenditure, which is the lowest in the world, and is less than 1% of the country's GDP (KPMG, 2005). Around 94% of the amount of private expenditure is from out of the pockets of citizens, and the remaining 6% is the provision's expenditure (Development Bank A, 2015). The way forward for the government to address this challenging situation is to consider the Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) model in the emergency healthcare sector in India. The emergence

of PPP in India has provided a viable solution wherein the government-led public sector forms a synergetic partnership with the technically advanced and innovative private sector (Raman, A.V et al., 2008). In emergency medical services, the government set-up 108 partnerships in 2005 (Besley, T., & Ghatak, M. 2017) with private organizations, such as GVK, Ziqitza Health Care Ltd., to deal with fatal emergencies, for example, dealing with the medical emergency during the Fani cyclone¹ at Odisha in 2019. However, the emergency services are fragmented in India (Subhan, I., & Jain, A. 2010), with many private services having entered the arena without regulation. Though this may look to be a good social and altruistic sign, in the long-run, it would hamper the progress of emergency services across the country. These questions will be well-addressed in this study when the rationality of promoting the emergency service systems is evaluated from the financing point of view. Further, in this study, we model the PPP contracts in accordance with the government's plan to integrate emergency services inclusive of fire and police with emergency health services under a common emergency telephone number, 112. Evidence is available to show that several roles, strategies, rules, and pay-offs govern procedures in the partnerships between the public sector and private firms (Bettignies, J.-E. de, & Ross, T. W, 2004). Thus, modeling them as complex games can help to better understand the failures and difficulties in such partnerships (Scharle, 2002). In this context, the researchers are implementing Nash bargain solutions in their research works to understand financial renegotiations (De Brux, J. 2010). However, there are very few studies to understand why financial renegotiation between government and service provider fails in a PPP contract. Through this study, we hope to provide a solid foundation to the integrated emergency medical services, which in turn, would provide Indian citizens the same equity, access, and quality of services which have been enjoyed by the people in the developing countries for decades.

¹ Fani cyclone hit many parts of Odisha in April- May of 2019, article by Vishwa Mohan (May 4, 2019), Times of India.

In the first essay, we have modeled funding mechanisms for Profit-based (Corporate) service providers to provide emergency medical services in PPP during natural disasters such as cyclones and tsunamis or pandemic-like situations such as Covid-19 when there is an unprecedented increase in demand of this service provision. In the second situation, that is, pandemic-like situations, we have considered modeling conditions when the service provider is successful in renegotiating with the government as well as when renegotiation is unsuccessful and investor goes ahead with the funding under government intervention.. Insights from the study indicate that government underinvests during regular situations, whereas during situations which require unprecedented rise in demand, it needs to monitor the service providers to prevent moral hazards.

In the second essay, we have modeled funding mechanisms for non-profit-based (NGO) service providers under similar conditions as in the first essay. Further, in case of an unprecedented rise of demand, we have restricted to modeling in renegotiation, as the case of renegotiation failure does not occur in case of non-profit-based service providers. Insights from the study show that the government has preference for investing in non-profit service providers as their pay-off increases with the payoff of the non-profit service provider (SP).

In the final essay, we have modeled advertising as a signal to convey the type of service provider (profit/non-profit) to the citizens (/Users/Patients); and also help the service providers decide their service provision. The study reveals that in regular situations, the advertisement strategy may aid to serve the patients when they require the emergency services. Further, the government may prefer either of the SPs (Profit-Oriented or Non-Profit-Oriented) to provide better payoffs in the PPP contractual relationship.

We find that the government needs to incentivize service providers to attain demand /service realization. Alternatively, it can penalize service providers by formulating policies if the effort

decreases with an increase in investment, as in few scenarios. Further, in all scenarios the government needs to formulate policies that aid investment in insurance companies so that citizens have to make less “out of pockets payments” that are quite expensive in emerging economies like India. Though insurance schemes have been launched by the central government in the past few years, various states that have been in PPP -based contracts for emergency health services need to coordinate with the centre to launch more innovative insurance schemes to reduce “out of pocket” expenses” thereby, improving citizen’s welfare.

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REFERENCES

1. Agheon Phillippe et al. (2000). Agency Costs, Firm Behavior and the Nature of Competition. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rie.2017.04.005>.
2. Akintoye A, Beck M, and Kumaraswamy, M (2016) Public Private Partnership: A Global Review (Edt) Routledge, London, ISBN 978-04-415-72896-
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315686516>
3. Alonso-Conde, A. B., Brown, C., & Rojo-Suarez, J. (2007). Public-private partnerships: Incentives, risk transfer, and real options. *Review of Financial Economics*, 16(4), 335–349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rfe.2007.03.002>
4. Auriol, E., & Picard, P. M. (2013). A theory of BOT concession contracts. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 89, 187-209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2011.10.003>.
5. Bagwell.K., and G. Ramey (1990). “Advertising and pricing to deter or accommodate entry when the demand is unknown.” *International Journal of Industrial Organization*,.93-113. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-7187\(89\)90036-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-7187(89)90036-2).
6. Baojun Jiang, Jian Ni and Kannan Srinivasan.(2014) “ Signaling Through Pricing by Service Providers with social preferences” *Marketing Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mksc.2014.0850>.
7. Baru, R. V. (2003). Privatisation of Health Services: A South Asian Perspective. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 38(42), 4433–4437. Accessed from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4414156>
8. Bennett, S. and Mills, A.(1998), 'Government capacity to contract: health sector experience and lessons,' *Public Administration and Development*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 307-326.[https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-162X\(1998100\)18:4307::AID:PAD24::3.0.CO;2-D](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-162X(1998100)18:4307::AID:PAD24::3.0.CO;2-D)
9. Michael Bergman & Jan-Erik Lane. (1990). Public Policy in a Principal-Agent Framework, *Journal of Theoretical Politics*, vol. 2(3), pages 339-352. Accessed from <https://ideas.repec.org/a/sae/jothpo/v2y1990i3p339-352.html>.

10. Besley, T., & Ghatak, M. (2017). Public-private partnerships for the provision of public goods: Theory and an application to NGOs. *Research in Economics*, 71(2), 356–371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rie.2017.04.005>.
11. Blanken, A., & Dewulf, G. (n.d.). PPPs in Health: Static or Dynamic? *The Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 69(S1), 35–47. <http://doi.org/10.29145/jmr.72.070204>
12. Buso, M. (2019). Bundling versus unbundling: asymmetric information on information externalities. *Journal of Economics*, 128(1), 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00712-018-0642-0>
13. Carr, B. G., Caplan, J. M., Pryor, J. P., & Branas, C. C. (2006). A Meta-Analysis of Prehospital Care Times for Trauma. *Prehospital Emergency Care*, 10(2), 198–206. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10903120500541324>
14. Casady, Carter B., Kent Eriksson, Raymond E. Levitt, and W. Richard Scott. 2020. “(Re)Defining Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in the New Public Governance (NPG) Paradigm: An Institutional Maturity Perspective.” *Public Management Review* 22, no. 2: 161-183. <http://doi:10.1080/14719037.2019.1577909>
15. CHO, I. and D.Kreps (1987) Signaling games and stable equilibrium. *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 102, 179-222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/1913604>
16. Chou, J.-S., Ping Tserng, H., Lin, C., & Yeh, C.-P. (2012). Critical factors and risk allocation for PPP policy: Comparison between HSR and general infrastructure projects. *Transport Policy*, 22, 36–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TRANPOL.2012.05.009>.
17. Cobb, Barry and Bawsuchoudhary, Atin.(2009) “ A Decision Analysis Approach to Solving the Signaling Game.” <https://doi.org/10.1287/deca.1090.0148>.
18. Chung, C. (2001). The Evolution of Emergency Medicine. *Hong Kong Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 8(2), 84–89. <https://doi.org/10.1177/102490790100800204>.
19. Cooley, Thomas F. and Bruce D. Smith (1987). Equilibrium in Cooperative Games of Policy Formulation. Working Paper No. 84, Rochester Centre of Economic Research. Accessed from https://rcer.econ.rochester.edu/RCERPAPERS/rcer_84.pdf

20. David, S. S., Vasnaik, M., & TV, R. (2007). Emergency medicine in India: Why are we unable to walk the talk *Emergency Medicine Australasia*, 19(4), 289–295. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-6723.2007.00985.x>
21. Baxter D, Casady CB. Proactive and Strategic Healthcare Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in the Coronavirus (Covid-19) Epoch. *Sustainability*. 2020; 12(12):5097. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su1212509>.
22. De Bettignies, J.-E., & Ross, T. W. (2004). The Economics of Public-Private Partnerships. *Canadian Public Policy / Analyse de Politiques*, 30(2), 135–154. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3552389>
23. De Brux, J. (2010). The Dark and Bright Sides of Renegotiation: An Application to Transport Concession Contracts. *Utilities Policy*, 18(2), 77–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2009.07.003>
24. Mehta, Anouj; Bhatia, Aparna; Chatterjee, Ameeta. 2010. *Improving Health and Education Service Delivery in India through Public-Private Partnerships*. © Asian Development Bank. Accessed from <http://hdl.handle.net/11540/1036>.
25. Dykstra, E. H. (1997). International models for the practice of emergency care. *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 15(2), 208–209. Accessed from [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-6757\(97\)90107-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-6757(97)90107-8)
26. Elitzur, R., & Gavious, A. (2003). Contracting, signaling, and moral hazard: a model of entrepreneurs, 'angels,' and venture capitalists. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 18(6), 709–725. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(03\)00027-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(03)00027-2)
27. Elitzur, R., & Gavious, A. (2011). Selection of entrepreneurs in the venture capital industry: An asymptotic analysis. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2011.06.029>.
28. Case Study on “Emergency Medical Service (EMS) in India: A Concept Paper” by National Health Systems Resource Centre (NHSRC) Technical Support Institution with National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India. Accessed from <https://fdocuments.in/document/ems-concept-paper.html>.

29. Sulakshana Nandi, Vandana Prasad, Deepika Joshi, Indira Chakravarthi, Ganapathy Murugan, Shahnawaz Khan, Mohammed Allam Ashraf, Pallavi Gupta, Chandan Kumar. (2021). *Public Private Partnerships in healthcare, Evidence from India*. Accessed from <https://epw.in/journal/2021/36/perspectives/public-private-partnerships-healthcare.html>
30. Gregory, A. W., & Hansen, B. E. (1996). Residual-based tests for cointegration in models with regime shifts. *Journal of Econometrics*, 70(1), 99–126. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076\(99\)00168-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076(99)00168-7).
31. Grimsey, D., & Lewis, M. (2007). Public Private Partnerships and Public Procurement. *Agenda: A Journal of Policy Analysis and Reform*, 14(2), 171–188. <https://doi.org/10.22459/AG.14.02.2007.06>
32. Gupta, M. Das, & Rani, M. (2004). *India's Public Health System: How Well Does It Function at the National Level?* The World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-3447>.
33. Felix Munoz-Garcia (2012). “A systematic procedure for finding perfect equilibria in Incomplete Information Games” vol. 6, no. 1, 2012, pp. <https://doi.org/10.1515/1935-5041.1049>
34. Frank A Sloan & Chee Ruey Hsieh (2017) *Health economics*. The MIT Press
Jan 27, 2017 | 840 Pages | 8 x 9 | ISBN 9780262035118.
35. Fudenberg, D., & Tirole, J. 1993. *Game Theory*. MIT Press. Cambridge . MA.
36. Gibbons, R. 1992 *Game Theory For economists*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ.
37. Hart, O. (2003). Incomplete Contracts and Public Ownership: Remarks, and an Application to Public-Private Partnerships. *The Economic Journal*, 113(486), C69–C76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0297.00119>
38. Hayllar, M. R., & Wettenhall, R. (2010). Public-Private Partnerships: Promises, Politics, and Pitfalls. *The Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 69(S1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2009.00657.x>
39. Ho, S. P. (2009). Government Policy on PPP Financial Issues: Bid Compensation and Financial Renegotiation. *Policy, Finance & Management for Public-Private Partnerships*, 267–300. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444301427.ch15>

40. Ho, Thomas S. Y. and Lee, Sang Bin, (2004), *The Oxford Guide to Financial Modeling: Applications for Capital Markets, Corporate Finance, Risk Management and Financial Institutions*, Oxford University Press. Accessed from <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:oxp:obooks:9780195169621>.
41. Huige Xing 1, Yuelin Li 1 and Hongyang Li 2,3, (2020). Renegotiation Strategy of Public-Private Partnership Projects with Asymmetric Information— An Evolutionary Game Approach. *Sustainability*, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072646>
42. Hung, K. K. C., Cheung, C. S. K., Rainer, T. H., & Graham, C. A. (2009). International EMS systems: China. *Resuscitation*, *80*, 732–735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resuscitation.2009.04.016>.
43. Kennedy, G. M. (2013). Can game theory be used to address PPP renegotiations ? A retrospective study of the of the Metronet - London Underground PPP By Dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of requirements for the degree of MSc in Business Administration, at the Univers, (June). Accessed from <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.14/15839>
44. Klijn, E. H., & Koppenjan, J. (2016). Public Money & Management The impact of contract characteristics on the performance of public-private partnerships (PPPs). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540962.2016.1206756>.
45. KPMG. (2015). *The Emerging Role of PPP in Indian Healthcare Sector Prepared By In collaboration with the Indian government*. [White Paper], Accessed from <https://www.ibef.org/download/PolicyPaper.pdf>
46. Kuruvilla, Sarosh & Liu, Mingwei & Jacob, Priti. (2005). A Case Study of the Yeshasvini Health Insurance Scheme for the Rural Poor in India. *International Journal of Self Help and Self Care*. 3. 261-306. 10.2190/D60U-5637-M315-3K57.
47. Liu, X., Hotchkiss, D. R., & Bose, S. (2007). The impact of contracting-out on health system performance: A conceptual framework. *Health Policy*, *82*, 200–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2006.09.012>
48. Lv, J., Ye, G., Liu, W., Shen, L., & Wang, H. (2015). Alternative Model for Determining the Optimal Concession Period in Managing BOT Transportation Projects. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, *31*(4), 04014066. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ME.1943-5479.0000291](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000291).

49. Madhurima Nundy and Rama V Baru. (2013). Private Partnerships of Boundaries: Public-Blurring in Health Services in India. *Economic Political Weekly*, 43(4), 62–71. Accessed from <https://www.epw.in/journal/2008/04>
50. MacAl, C. M., & North, M. J. (2010). Tutorial on agent-based modeling and simulation. *Journal of Simulation*, 4(3), 151–162. Accessed from <https://doi.org/10.1057/jos.2010.3>
51. Manigart, S., De Waele, K., Wright, M., Robbie, K., Desbrières, P., Sapienza, H. J., & Beekman, A. (2002). Determinants of required return in venture capital investments: a five-country study. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 17(4), 291–312. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(00\)00067-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(00)00067-7)
52. Mason, C. M., & Harrison, R. T. (2002). Is it worth it? The rates of return from informal venture capital investments. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 17(3), 211–236. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(00\)00060-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(00)00060-4)
53. Medda, F. R., Carbonaro, G., & Davis, S. L. (2013). Public-private partnerships in transportation: Some insights from the European experience. *IATSS Research*, 36(2), 83–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IATSSR.2012.11.002>
54. Mitroff, I. I., & Mason, R. O. (2011). The Metaphysics of Policy and Planning: A Reply to Cosier. *Academy of Management Review*, 6(4), 649–651. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1981.4285721>
55. Sethi, Nitin & Rao, Menaka. (2017) NITI Aayog and health ministry prepare model contract for privatizing urban health care. *Scroll.in*. Accessed from <https://scroll.in/pulse/844272/niti-aayog-and-health-ministry-prepare-model-contract-for-privatising-urban-health-care>
56. Oliveira Cruz, C., & Cunha Marques, R. (2014). Theoretical Considerations on Quantitative PPP Viability Analysis. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ME.1943-5479.0000184](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000184)
57. Prakash, G., & Singh, A. (2010). *A New Public Management Perspective in Indian E-Governance Initiatives*. Accessed from https://www.csi-sigegov.org/critical_pdf/8_71-80.pdf
58. Raman, A. V., Björkman, J. W., & Björkman, J. W. (2008). *Public-Private Partnerships in Health Care in India*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203886557>
59. Roberts, M. J., Hsiao, W., Berman, P., & Reich, M. R. (2008.). Getting Health Reform Right. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195371505.001.0001>.

60. Ross, T. W., & Yan, J. (2015). Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice Comparing Public-Private Partnerships and Traditional Public Procurement: Efficiency vs. Flexibility. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 17(5), 448–466. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13876988.2015.1029333>
61. Schneider, S. M., Gardner, A. F., Weiss, L. D., Wood, J. P., Ybarra, M., Beck, D. M., Jouriles, N. J. (2010). The Future of Emergency Medicine. *The Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 39(2), 210–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JEMERMED.2010.06.001>
62. Serra, Danila & Serneels, Pieter & Barr, Abigail,(2010)."Intrinsic Motivations and the Non-Profit Health Sector: Evidence from Ethiopia," IZA Discussion Papers 4746, Institute of Labor Economics. Accessed from <https://ideas.repec.org/p/iza/izadps/dp4746.html>.
63. Shi, L., Zhang, L., Onishi, M., Kobayashi, K., & Dai, D. (2018). Contractual Efficiency of PPP Infrastructure Projects: An Incomplete Contract Model. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2018, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/3631270>
64. Singh, A., & Prakash, G. (2010). Public-Private Partnerships in Health Services Delivery. *Public Management Review*, 12(6), 829–856. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2010.488860>
65. Spence. M (1973) "Job Market Signaling" *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 87, pp 355-371. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1882010>
66. Sharma M, Brandler ES (2014). Emergency medical services in India: the present and future. *Prehosp Disaster Med*. 2014;29(3):307-310. <https://doi:10.1017/S1049023X14000296>
67. Subhan, I., & Jain, A. (2010). Emergency care in India: the building blocks. *International Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 3(4), 207–211. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12245-010-0223-7>
68. Titoria, R., & Mohandas, A. (2019). A glance on public-private partnership: an opportunity for developing nations to achieve universal health coverage. *International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health*, 6(3), 1353. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20190640>
69. Tserng, H. P., Russell, J. S., Hsu, C. W., & Lin, C. (2012). Analyzing the role of national PPP units in promoting PPPs: Using new institutional economics and a case study. *Journal of construction engineering and management*, 138(2), 242-249. [http://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0000398](http://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0000398)

70. Ho, T.S.Y & Lee, S.B. (2004). *The Oxford Guide to Financial Modelling: Applications for Capital Markets, Corporate Finance, Risk Management and Financial Institutions*. OUP Publishers, USA. <https://doi.org/10.2469/faj.v62.n2.4088>.
71. Vasudevan, V., Singh, P., & Basu, S. (2016). Importance of awareness in improving performance of emergency medical services (EMS) systems in enhancing traffic safety: A lesson from India. *Traffic Injury Prevention, 17*(7), 699–704. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15389588.2016.1163689>
72. Venkitasubramanian, Akshay, (2010). A Study of PPP Models for Social Healthcare Insurance. Centre for public policy research. Accessed from <https://www.cppr.in/wpcontent/uploads/2012/03/A-Study-of-PPP-Models-for-Social-Healthcare-Insurance-Akshay-V.pdf>
73. Wibowo, A., & Alfen, H. W. (2015a). Critical success factors in public-private partnership (PPP) on infrastructure delivery in Nigeria. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration, 5*(1), 212–225. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BEPAM-03-2014-0016>
74. Wibowo, A., & Alfen, H. W. (2015b). Government-led critical success factors in PPP infrastructure development. *Built Environment Project and Asset Management, 5*(1), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BEPAM-03-2014-0016>
75. X Guo & B Jiang(2016).Signaling through price and quality to consumers with fairness concerns”. *Journal of Marketing Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmr.15.0323>